

The Geodemographic Classification of Interactivity for Greater London

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Summary

Geodemographic classifications have been traditionally used to characterise individuals based on where they live or work. As a further contribution to understanding how social systems function, their scope is extensible to incorporating human *interactivity*, that is the generalised activity patterns of the population beyond night-time residence or workplace. This is enabled by dynamic sources of data such as GPS in-app mobile phone location data, creating the possibility of incorporating such data and gaining a more holistic understanding of the day-to-day activities and interactions of individuals. This paper therefore develops the geodemographic classification of interactivity for Greater London, using a combination of data sources, including census 2021 data and GPS in-app mobile phone location data.

KEYWORDS: geodemographics; in-app location data; temporal analytics; interactional geographies

1. Introduction

Geodemographics are a well-established geo-spatial approach used to analyse socio-economic and demographic information about people and associating it to where they live (Longley, 2015). A static representation of the population is prevalent in past geodemographic research (Adnan et al. 2010), and population has been mostly characterised by variables pertaining to their normal place of residence or work. This paper creates a geodemographic classification of interactivity for Greater London, with the primary goal of enhancing conventional geodemographic classifications, by incorporating measures of interaction that capture more of the everyday lives of individuals. Areas are not only differentiated by the characteristics of the resident population but also by how interactive and socially engaged they are. This is achieved by conceptually respecifying neighbourhood classification to build upon the past classifications. Census variables provide a solid foundation for understanding the socio-demographic characteristics of the resident population and thus make up one of the domains of the classification. We are then using an additional domain that captures functional and interactional characteristics which on the contrary describe how these areas are used dynamically.

- i. Socio-economic and demographic domain
- ii. Functional and interactional characteristics domain
 - a. Connectivity characteristics sub-domain
 - b. Diurnal activity and functions sub-domain
 - c. Service accessibility sub-domain

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This paper presents the rationale for incorporating variables from additional data sources in geodemographic classifications. It then presents the methodology followed to create the classification and the resulting classification and profiles associated with each cluster. Finally, the paper explores the possible applications of the newly created classification.

2. Background

Amongst some past geodemographic classifications are the Output Area Classifications (OACs) which develop general characterisations of the core domains of successive censuses (Vickers et al., 2007; Gale et al., 2016; Wyszomierski et al., 2024). They provide widely used and readily intelligible small area classifications of night-time populations. However, despite inclusion of data representing employment activities, they do not aspire to portray the functional characteristics of residential neighbourhoods. Latterly, employment activities have been characterised by workplace zone classifications (Cockings et al. 2020) but no other activities (including, by and large, homeworking). By expanding beyond just census data, it becomes possible to obtain a more nuanced and dynamic understanding of over-all activity patterns, thereby also deepening the remit of geodemographics to accommodate the juxtapositioning of different land uses (locational proximity) alongside the social similarities that characterise different neighbourhoods. Interactional data allow us to specify locational proximity of different land use functions, specifically with respect to how well-connected areas are.

This research proposes a novel classification that adds information about the interactional geographies of an output area, as well as its accessibility characteristics and footfall throughout the day. This is driven by the hypothesis that certain output areas are more well-connected than others and that their functions are influenced by both the people that reside there as well as by their varying footfall throughout the day. The selection of the variables used to create the geodemographic classification of interactivity can be found in **Appendix 1**. This classification builds on the work presented by the authors at GISRUK 2024 which uses GPS in-app mobile phone location data to understand origin-destination flows between MSOAs at different times of day (Mavrogeni et al. 2024). By applying this data to the more granular scale of OAs, we generate several interaction-focused variables (making up the connectivity characteristics, and diurnal activity and functions sub-domains), including total intra- and inter-OA flows, connections to first- and second-order neighbours, and the proportion of inbound flows within three-hour time window. In addition to these dynamic variables, the classification incorporates census data, accessibility metrics, and crime levels to offer a comprehensive understanding of OAs' daytime and nighttime population characteristics and functions.

3. Methods

This research develops and extends the methodological workflow of previous geodemographic classifications. This is due to their success in creating effective population characterisations as well as due to the similar variable structure (Vickers et al., 2007; Gale et al., 2016; Cockings et al., 2020; Wyszomierski et al., 2024).

Firstly, all variables are transformed to avoid data skewness and ensure that the variables are as close to normal distribution as possible. Whilst past classifications have utilised the Inverse Hyperbolic Sine (IHS) transformation, it was considered more appropriate to use a combination of various transformation methods to find the one that works best for each variable. Whilst the IHS transformation works well with the census variables, it is shown to be less effective when applied to our interactivity variables.

The next step in the data pre-processing, is data standardisation which is used to ensure that the variables are placed on the same scale. Decile standardisation was used, because it increases the emphasis on the tails of the distribution, which can highlight extreme values and exaggerate variations in the data. It divides the data into ten equal-sized groups, ensuring there is an equal number of

observations in each decile.

Then, the variables are tested for multicollinearity which occurs when the correlation between two variables is close to 1 or -1. This is problematic because the highly correlated variables' influence in the final classification will be over-exaggerated. There is no specific rule to denote the cutoff for multicollinear variables, however the most prevalent one used in past research is a Pearson correlation value higher than 0.6 or 0.7 (Gale et al., 2016; Wyszomierski et al., 2024).

An important requirement when selecting the appropriate clustering method is to ensure that it both works well with the size of the dataset and the multidimensionality of the indicators, as well as that it doesn't introduce unnecessary complexity to the model (Wyszomierski et al., 2024). K-means clustering was selected amongst other alternatives following past geodemographic classifications (Vickers and Ress, 2007; Adnan et al., 2010; Gale et al., 2016; Walford and Armitage, 2020).

Cluster optimisation is a crucial step taken to decide on the suitable number of k clusters. One method is to use Clustergrams which effectively visualise the re-distribution of data with each additional component/cluster, as well as the size of each component/cluster (depicted through the size of the red dots in **Figure 1**). The Clustergram clearly shows that the optimum solution has seven clusters, since one of the aims is to keep between cluster variation as large as possible. Further partitioning of the data results in two clusters that are poorly differentiated, whilst selecting a lower number of solutions (4-6) would limit the extent to which data is differentiated.

Figure 1: Clustergram showing the partitioning of the data points into clusters

4. Results

Figure 2 presents the geodemographic classification of interactivity, dividing London's output areas into 7 separate clusters. A brief look at the spatial distribution of clusters, shows that central London OAs are part of the same cluster (Cluster 7). Clusters 4 and 5 and 6 form around central London output areas, and intertwine with each other, whilst Clusters 1 and 2 form in suburban neighbourhoods and

group together multiple OAs forming self-contained clusters. Lastly, Cluster 3 forms in the suburbs of Greater London, and mostly includes non-built up output areas.

Figure 2: The geodemographic classification of interactivity

To understand the contribution of the different variables in each cluster's composition, **Figure 3** can be used to assess each variable's cluster mean, in relation to the global mean. Values above zero denote variables present in the cluster at higher values than the global average level. Conversely, values below zero indicate variables below the global average in the cluster. Variable numbers can be matched to the variable names in **Appendix 1**.

Figure 3: Cluster-wise averages of variables

The numbers in **Figure 3** can be translated into cluster descriptions which have been summarised and presented in **Table 1**, along with the proposed cluster labels.

Table 1: Cluster pen-portraits

Cluster	Label	Short description
Cluster 1	Leisure hubs with high connectivity (12.2%)	High footfall due to leisure activities, and high connectivity, but lower accessibility to typical amenities. Includes major transport nodes like Heathrow and London City airports.
Cluster 2	Low connectivity residential zones (19.1%)	Primarily residential, low interactivity and connectivity, high visits during late hours (possibly night workers returning home).
Cluster 3	Suburban daytime locales (17.5%)	Suburban, family-oriented, low leisure activity, strong first-order connections but weak broader connectivity. Daytime visits dominate.
Cluster 4	Morning-active elite residential and park areas (11.3%)	Predominantly affluent residential and park areas, high inbound flows in the morning (6am–3pm), likely due to local residents running errands or visiting parks, strong connections to immediate neighbours, include

		prestigious London neighbourhoods such as Kensington, Chelsea, and Hampstead
Cluster 5	Central youth and leisure zones (13.4%)	Close to central London, high leisure activity, vibrant night and early morning visits, high interactivity but low first- and second-order connections.
Cluster 6	Professional urban bases with high accessibility (15.5%)	Young professionals, high qualifications, high accessibility, low leisure visits, compact inbound flows (6pm–3am), and high connectivity.
Cluster 7	Central dynamic mix (11.1%)	Central London areas with diverse activities, high accessibility and connectivity, significant night and day activity, appealing to workers and visitors alike.

5. Conclusions

This research has built and introduced the geodemographic classification of interactivity. Unlike other well-known geodemographic classifications such as the Output Area Classification and Workplace Zone Classification which characterise people by where they live and work respectively, the geodemographic classification of interactivity characterises an area based on a combination of factors including the residents' characteristics, interactivity, connectivity and types of activity the area is involved in. This can in turn benefit policy makers and urban planners by enabling better-targeted public services that are responsive to the changing use of space throughout the day, and by designing spaces that meet the needs of both the resident population, and those who use the area for work or leisure. Additionally, by incorporating interactional data and footfall, the classification captures dimensions of social similarity that traditional geodemographic classifications might miss. This research can also be used as a proof of concept, i.e., as a means for introducing a new way of framing interactions within geodemographics. We have therefore built a classification that is generalisable and identifies the presence of general patterns across neighbourhoods, as well as the unique OA-specific interactional characteristics, thus creating a holistic picture of the relationship between people and places.

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Biographies

Mikaella Mavrogeni is a PhD student co-funded by UBEL DTP and Didobi, with project title ‘Real-time Geodemographics for business and service planning’. Research interests include using geo-spatial data to analyse population mobility such as deriving activity patterns from location data and creating origin-destination matrices from public transport data.

Paul Longley is Professor of Geographic Information Science at University College London, where he directs the Economic and Social Research Council-funded Consumer Data Research Centre.

Justin van Dijk is a Lecturer in Social and Geographic Data Science in the Department of Geography at University College London. His primary research interests are grouped around the analysis and visualisation of large-scale spatial data and socio-spatial inequalities.

Appendix 1: Classification variables and descriptions

Variable code	Variable Name	Description	Domain	Sub-domain
1	One Person household	Household composition	SOCIO-ECONOMIC AND DEMOGRAPHIC	
2	Families with no children			
3	Families with dependent children			
4	Aged 4 years and under	Age group		
5	Aged 5 to 14			
6	Aged 15 to 24			
7	Aged 25 to 34			

8	Aged 35 to 44			
9	Aged 45 to 64			
10	Aged 65 to 84			
11	Aged 85 years and over			
12	Ownership or shared ownership	Tenure		
13	Private rented			
14	L15 Full time students	NS-SeC		
15	SOC1: Managers, directors and senior officials	Occupation		
16	SOC2: Professional occupations			
17	SOC3: Associate professional and technical occupations			
18	SOC4: Administrative and secretarial occupations			
19	SOC5: Skilled trade occupations			
20	SOC6: Caring, leisure and service occupations			
21	SOC7: Sales and customer service occupations			
22	SOC8: Process, plant and machine operatives			
23	SOC9: Elementary occupations			

24	Economically active: Employed	Economic activity Status		
25	Economically active: Unemployed			
26	Economically inactive			
27	Level 4 qualifications or above	Highest level of qualification		
28	Standardised Illness Ration (SIR)	Long term health and disability		
29	Crime level by km ²	Street-level crime by crime type, date and longitude/latitude coordinates, openly available and reported through the Metropolitan Police here		
30	Total first order neighbour interactions	the total number of times the OA had a flow to or from a neighbouring OA considered a first order neighbour		
31	Total second order neighbour interactions	the total number of times the OA had a flow to or from a neighbouring OA considered a second order neighbour		
32	Proportion of first order neighbours connected	The proportion of first order neighbours an OA is connected to		
33	Proportion of second order neighbours connected	The proportion of second order neighbours an OA is connected to		
34	Total OAs the OA of interest has interacted with	the range of connections between OAs whether origin or destination		
35	Total interaction flows with other OAs (inter flows)	the volume of connections between OAs		

36	Total interactions within the OA (intra flows)	the volume of connections within an OA		
37	Range of distances from OA	range of distances travelled from the OA of interest to all other destination OAs		
38	Range of distance to OA	range of distances travelled from other origin OAs to the OA of interest		
39	Place of residence	the total number of times the OA was visited at the location of residence		
40	Leisure	the total number of times the OA was visited at a place for leisure purposes		
41	Visits to the OA between 12am and 3am	Aggregated interaction flows ending in each Output Area, aggregated by 3-hour time window.		
42	Visits to the OA between 3am and 6am			
43	Visits to the OA between 6am and 9am			
44	Visits to the OA between 9am and 12pm			
45	Visits to the OA between 12pm and 3pm			
46	Visits to the OA between 3pm and 6pm			
47	Visits to the OA between 6pm and 9pm			
48	Visits to the OA between 9pm and 12am			
			Diurnal activity and functions	

49	Total employment opportunities within 45 minutes	Uses employment data from the Business Register and Employment survey, point and polygon data downloaded through OpenStreetMap in RStudio, along with OSM network data and GTFS data from Rail Delivery Group for rail and Department for Transport for Bus/Tube timetables		Service accessibility
50	Total supermarkets within 30 minutes			
51	Total hospitals and GPs within 30 minutes			
52	Total schools within 45 minutes			